

Convolutional Neural Network Algorithm using MobileNet and VGG19 Architectures for Human Skin Disease Classification based on Web and Mobile Applications

Prof. Dr. Sunardi Sangsang Sasmowiyono

Vice Rector, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Email: sunardi@mti.uad.ac.id

ORCID:

Abstract

A harsh environment, drastic weather changes, or sensitivity to various allergies has encouraged humans to maintain their health, including skin as the outermost organ. Besides being physically visible and noticeable, abnormal skin can impact to the mental health, sometimes making sufferers feel embarrassed or reluctant to see a doctor, especially if the location is remote, requires time and transportation, or is expensive cost. To address this, technological assistance is needed as an initial solution so that the people can independently detect the human skin conditions or complaints early. If a person is indicated to have a certain disease, appropriate and fast treatment can be done immediately or verification and other necessary follow-up can be carried out.

There are various skin diseases based on their causes, severity, impacts, treatment, and so on. This research focuses on classifying the human skin diseases using application of website and Android mobile so that anyone can perform the initial detection and classification independently, effectively, and efficiently. The data used consisted of 3,295 images of human skin diseases retrieved from Kaggle. The data were divided into a normal class and five classes according to disease type: acne and rosacea, chickenpox, eczema, ringworm, and seborrheic keratoses.

Human skin disease classification was performed using a Convolutional Neural Network. Model evaluation was performed using confusion metrics. The model built with the MobileNet architecture achieved the best results with 93.09% accuracy, 93.14% precision, 93.09% recall, and 93.03% f1-score. These results were superior to those of the VGG19 architecture, which achieved 91.29% accuracy, 91.72% precision, 91.29% recall, and 91.38% f1-score. The model on the website-based system and Android mobile has been well implemented.

Keywords: *confusion metrics, convolutional neural network, human skin disease, mobileNet, VGG19*